

Synthetic approach, characterization, superoxide dismutase and antimicrobial activities of imidazolate-bridged Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}, Cu^{II}-Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} binuclear complexes with amino acid derived Schiff bases

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Manuscript received online 18 March 2016, accepted 28 March 2016

Abstract : Synthetic and characterization of several imidazolato-bridged binuclear transition metal complexes viz. [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na 1; [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na 2; [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na 3; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na 4; [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(L²)]Na 5; where H₂L = (*E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) acetic acid ; H₂L¹ = (*S,E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) propanoic acid; H₂L² = (*R*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-3-methylbutanoic acid, Im = imidazolate ion, have been described. The value of magnetic moment at room temperature showed that the imidazole group can mediate antiferromagnetic interactions for 1-5. Amino acids derived Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) were synthesized by the condensation of equimolar (1 : 1) ratio of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde with glycine, alanine and valine, respectively, dissolved in ethanol. Superoxide dismutase activity of all these metal complexes has been revealed to catalyze the dismutation of superoxide (O₂⁻) and IC₅₀ values were evaluated. The *in vitro* antimicrobial activities of metal complexes 1-5 of H₂L-H₂L² have been investigated and compared with reported complexes.

Keywords : Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}/Cu^{II}-Zn^{II}/Cu^{II}-Ni^{II} complexes, imidazolate-bridged, antiferromagnetic spin exchange, superoxide dismutase, antimicrobial, amino acid derived Schiff bases.

Introduction

Copper is one of the transition elements frequently found at the active site of many enzymes and proteins, which play a key role in biology. The copper containing enzymes and proteins constitute an important class of biologically active compounds/model compounds. The biological functions of copper proteins/enzymes include electro transfer, dioxygen transport, oxygenation, oxidation, reduction, and disproportionation¹.

Synthetic binuclear transition metal complexes provide models for metalloproteins active sites and lend inside towards the design of new catalysts. Interest in imidazolato-bridged binuclear metal complexes like [Cu^{II}-Im-Zn^{II}-SOD] has increased due to the involvement

imidazolate ion as a bridging ligand between Cu^{II} ion and Zn^{II} ions (Scheme 1) in the Cu, Zn-superoxide dismutase enzyme²⁻⁵. In recent years, application of SODs as therapeutic agent has attracted much attention, because of the harmful effect of the O₂⁻ ion *in vivo*⁶⁻⁸. Oberley and Buettner⁹ have reported that cancer cells had less superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity than normal cells. As superoxide ion is toxic to cells; a defense mechanism must have been initiated by nature. We know that essentially all organisms, which use dioxygen and many that have to survive an oxygenated environment, contain at least one superoxide dismutase (SOD). The one which is pertinent to this article is a Cu, Zn protein found in cells that contain a nucleus (eukaryotic cells). X-Ray crystallographic

studies^{2,3} have shown that the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions exist in distorted square planar and tetrahedral coordination environments, respectively. A copper, zinc-superoxide model shows bio-catalytic activity towards the dismutation of superoxide anion according to the following equations¹⁰.

The deprotonated form of imidazole can serve as a bridging N₁, N₃ bidentate ligand for transition metal ions¹¹. In the last decades many bioinorganic studies were developed on mimetic complexes of imidazolite-bridged dependent proteins and have been characterized as active site structural and functional models for [Cu₂, Cu₂-SOD], [Cu₂, Ni₂-SOD] or [Cu₂, Zn₂-SOD]^{12,13}. They involve the pairs of either identical or dissimilar metals bridged by a deprotonated imidazole type molecule. Consequently, a number of model compounds have been prepared. Some metal complexes may be expected to be biologically active. All these complexes exhibit antiferromagnetic spin exchange interactions.

With this point in view, here, we present synthetic approach, characterization, superoxide dismutase and antimicrobial activities of binuclear imidazolite-bridged Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}, Cu^{II}-Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} complexes with amino acid derived Schiff base ligands as a models of Cu, Zn-superoxide dismutase. The binuclear complexes that have been characterized appeared to be good models for the active site in Cu₂, Cu₂-SOD, Cu₂, Ni₂-SOD and Cu₂, Zn₂-SOD subunits. The complexes was formulated as [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1**; [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2**; [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **3**; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4**; [(L²)Cu-Im-Cu(L²)]Na **5**. Very few imidazolite-bridged binuclear Cu^{II}-Cu^{II} and Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} complexes have been reported so far¹¹⁻¹³. The amino acid derived Schiff bases H₂L-H₂L² are diprotic ligand typically act as tridentate, planar chelate ligand coordinating through phenolic-O, azomethine-N and carboxylate-O atom (Scheme 2). The SOD activities have been measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger.

Experimental

Materials used for synthesis :

Copper perchlorate hexahydrate, nickel perchlorate

Scheme 1. Structure of the active center of the copper, zinc-superoxide dismutase enzyme.

hexahydrate and imidazole (Aldrich) were used as supplied. All the chemicals and solvents used were synthetic grade and used without further purification.

Instrumentation :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units) as standard reference. EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series Spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band with 100 kHz modulation frequency at room temperature and at 77 K. TCNE was used as field marker. The FT-IR spectra of the Schiff base ligands and their corresponding binuclear metal complexes were taken by the KBr technique, in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ wave number range. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities were evaluated using the following methods. The *in vitro* SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O₂⁻) and nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O₂⁻ scavenger¹⁴. A unit of SOD activity is concentration of complex, which causes 50% inhibition of alkaline DMSO mediated reduction of nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT). Filter paper disc diffusion plate method of Vinecent and Vinecent¹⁵ was used to test the *in vitro* antibacterial activities of synthesized complexes. The chosen strains were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi*.

Preparations :

Synthesis of Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) :

Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) were prepared by standard literature procedure^{16,17} and recrystallized from ethanol or methanol. Their purity was checked by elemental analysis.

The Schiff base ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) was synthesized

Scheme 2. Proposed structures and synthetic procedure of amino acid derived Schiff bases ($H^2L-H_2L^2$).

by refluxing 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (20 mmol, 4.02 g) with glycine (20 mmol, 1.50 g), alanine (20 mmol, 1.78 g) and valine (20 mmol, 2.32 g), respectively, in ethanol for 2–4 h; crystals appeared immediately after cooling to RT. The crystalline solid was filtered off, washed with ethanol, and dried in air and stored in $CaCl_2$ desiccators at room temperature. Yield : 90–95%.

Preparations of imidazole-bridged (Im) complexes 1-5 :

Imidazole-bridged (Im) homo/hetero binuclear complexes **1-5** were prepared by the published method¹⁸. Their purity was checked by CHN analysis.

Synthesis of homo-binuclear $Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}$ complex 1 :

The complexes were prepared by the following gen-

eral procedure : Aqueous solutions of copper perchlorate hexahydrate (2.0 mmol, 0.740 g) and H₂L (2.0 mmol, 1.50 g) and imidazole (1.0 mmol, 0.320 g) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred well. The pH of this stirred solution was raised to 10.0 by adding 1 M NaOH and the contents were left overnight at room temperature. Coloured products of [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1** was separated out. The samples were collected by filtration, washed with ethanol and dried in anhydrous CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield : 80%. Complex [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1** gave satisfactory elemental analyses (Table 1).

solutions was raised to 11. The solutions were left overnight at room temperature. The coloured crystalline products of [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na **3** ; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4** and [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(L²)]Na **5** was isolated. Complex [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2**, was also synthesized by the above synthesized method. Nickel perchlorate hexahydrate was used as a source of nickel. The samples were collected by filtration, washed with ethanol and dried in anhydrous CaCl₂ desiccator. Yield : 80–90%. All the Schiff bases and their corresponding metal complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data for binuclear imidazolate-bridged complexes **1-5**

Ligands and metal their complexes	Colour	$\mu_{\text{eff.}}$ (B.M.)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					
				C	H	N	Cu	Zn	Ni
H ₂ L	Red		90	41.89 (41.90)	3.12 (3.14)	5.43 (5.45)	–	–	–
H ₂ L ¹	Yellow		95	44.14 (44.16)	3.70 (3.72)	5.15 (5.17)	–	–	–
H ₂ L ²	Green		90	48.02 (48.04)	4.70 (4.72)	4.67 (4.69)	–	–	–
[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na 1	Blue	1.48	80	34.52 (34.56)	2.19 (2.23)	7.67 (7.71)	17.40 (17.43)	–	–
[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na 2	Green	1.75	70	34.77 (34.80)	2.22 (2.26)	7.72 (7.76)	8.76 (8.78)	–	8.09 (8.11)
[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na 3	Blue	1.77	65	34.45 (34.49)	2.20 (2.24)	7.65 (7.68)	8.68 (8.70)	8.93 (8.96)	–
[(L ¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L ¹)]Na 4	Blue	1.79	70	36.34 (36.36)	2.65 (2.67)	7.37 (7.41)	8.36 (8.38)	8.60 (8.63)	–
[(L ²)Cu-Im-Zn(L ²)]Na 5	Green	1.78	75	39.73 (39.76)	3.46 (3.49)	6.86 (6.90)	7.79 (7.82)	8.01 (8.04)	–

Synthesis of hetero-binuclear Cu^{II}-Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} complexes :

The complexes were prepared by the following general procedure : Copper perchlorate hexahydrate (2.0 mmol, 0.740 g) with H₂L (2.0 mmol, 1.50 g), H₂L¹ (2.0 mmol, 1.78 g) and H₂L² (2.0 mmol, 2.32 g), respectively (Set A) was dissolve in 50% water-methanol mixed solvent. Similarly, zinc perchlorate hexahydrate (2.0 mmol, 0.744 g) with H₂L (2.0 mmol, 1.50 g), H₂L¹ (2.0 mmol, 1.78 g) and H₂L² (2.0 mmol, 2.32 g), respectively, was dissolve in 50% water-methanol, 50 : 50 v/v (Set B). Both sets (Set A and Set B) of solutions were stirred well separately and then mixed together and stirred again for half an hour. By adding 1 M NaOH solution, the pH of

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The synthetic imidazole-bridged (Im) homo-hetero binuclear complexes were prepared by the following sequential routes without isolation of the mononuclear species.

where, M = Zn^{II}/Ni^{II} for hetero-binuclear complexes; A = (*E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) acetic acid (H₂L); (*S,E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) propanoic acid (H₂L¹); (*R*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-3-methylbutanoic acid (H₂L²); Im = imidazolate ion. All synthesized imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes give satisfactory elemental analysis (Table 1). The Schiff base ligands were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and glycine, alanine and valine, respectively, in ethanol for 2–4 h (Scheme 2). The proposed structures of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes **1-5** of H₂L-H₂L² was given in Scheme 3 and Scheme 4. The H₂L-H₂L² is diprotic ligand typically act as tridentate, planar chelate ligand coordinating through phenolic-O atom, azomethine-N and carboxylate-O atom. The present imidazolate-bridged complexes of H₂L-H₂L² was appears to be a fairly good models for the copper(II) site of intact Cu₂, Zn₂SOD because these showed several structural and spectroscopic features similar to the active site of the enzyme. These synthetic metal complexes may be expected to be biologically active.

Magnetic moments :

The room temperature effective magnetic moments

values (μ_{eff}) for the investigated homo-/hetero-binuclear complexes are given in Table 1 along with their physical data. The value of magnetic moment at room temperature allows to suppose that the homo-binuclear complexes are built up by the antiferromagnetic coupled binuclear cluster ($S = 1$ state) and that the magnetism of the hetero-binuclear complexes are due to the unpaired one-spin system ($S = 1/2$ state), with mild intermolecular interactions. The homo-binuclear complex **1** has substantially reduced magnetic moments (1.48 B.M.), consistent with proposed Cu-Im-Cu dimeric structures, suggesting the possibility of spin-coupled system. This behavior is ascribed to a paramagnetic species containing two antiferromagnetically coupled Cu^{II} ions. The antiferromagnetic behavior occurs when Cu-Im-Cu linkage connects the two copper(II) coordination spheres at axial sites of two square planar units. As expected, room temperature magnetic moments values of hetero-binuclear complexes **2-5** differ markedly from that of the homo-binuclear Cu^{II}-Cu^{II} complex **1**. The observed room temperature magnetic moments were around 1.75–1.79 B.M., in agreement with an unpaired one spin ($S = 1/2$) system¹⁹.

Infrared spectral investigation :

Present complexes were characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy. The IR spectrum of the metal complexes was compared with those of free ligands (H₂L-H₂L²) in order to determine the involvement of the coordination sites in the chelation. Analysis by FT-IR results in the absorption spectra in the infrared region and register bands or signals. IR spectrum of the H₂L-H₂L² ligands exhibited the most characteristic bands at 1635–1640 cm⁻¹ $\nu(>C=N-$, azomethine-N), 3150–3240 cm⁻¹ $\nu(>C-OH$, phenolic-OH), and 1390–1470 cm⁻¹ $\nu(>C-O$, carboxylate-O atom). The formation of Schiff bases, (*E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) acetic acid; (*S,E*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) propionic acid; (*R*)-2-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-3-methylbutanoic acid, was noted from the absence of C=O and NH₂ peaks in the ligands (Scheme 2). A strong band observed at *ca.* 1215–1330 cm⁻¹ was assigned to coordination through phenolic OH. The bands with a maximum of 3025–3040 cm⁻¹ (ν_{N-H}), characteristics for imidazole disappeared in the spectra of the metal complexes, indicating the presence of the imidazolate ion. The perchlorate ion shows a T_d symmetry, which is characteristics for the free ion,

Scheme 3. The proposed structures of imidazole-bridged binuclear Schiff base complexes of H_2L .

supporting that it does not take part in the coordination around the metal ions. The bands maximums of the deformation vibrations of the molecules do not change drastically, but their intensities increased. This fact indicates to the binuclear complexes, indicating also the formation of binuclear metal complexes with the suggestive structures²⁰ (Schemes 3 and 4). The IR data of ligands and their corresponding binuclear metal complexes showed that the Schiff bases were coordinated to the metal ion in a tridentate manner (ONO donor sites).

FAB-mass spectra :

The FAB-mass spectra suggested that the present binuclear complexes **1-5** showed dimeric nature. These complexes showed molecular ion peaks in good agreement with the empirical formula of which was given in Table 1.

Thus, mass spectra of the complexes $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ **1**, $[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ **2**, $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na$ **3**, $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(L^1)]Na$ **4** and $[(L^2)Cu-Im-Zn(L^2)]Na$ **5**, as representative complexes, showed the highest mass peaks at m/z at 730, 725, 732, 760 and 816, respectively, which agree well with the formula weights of the binuclear complexes²¹.

Electron paramagnetic resonance studies :

X-band EPR spectra of homo-/hetero-binuclear complexes were recorded at LNT (liquid nitrogen temperature) as well as RT (room temperature). Basic spectral characteristics at both temperatures are the same with slightly better resolution at LNT. Conforming the magnetic measurements, the spectra of homo-binuclear complex **1** showed the spectral features of an

Scheme 4. The proposed structures of imidazole-bridged binuclear complexes of H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 .

antiferromagnetically coupled binuclear species : (i) The $\Delta M_s = \pm$ 'half filled' signals is observed at 1700 G, (ii) $\Delta M_s = \pm 1$ region shows two broad signals at -2960 G and 3200 G (RT) and is characteristics of isotropic spectral feature. This type of transitions at 'half filled' is due to magnetic exchange interactions. Although magnetic moments values for these complexes except [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1** were found corresponding to one spin only. The calculated value of g_{iso} is given in Table 2. The spectra of hetero-binuclear complexes are characteristics of $S = 1$. A representative EPR spectrum of complex [(L)Cu-Im-

Table 2. EPR parameters (100% DMSO) for imidazolite-bridged binuclear complexes **1-5**

Complexes	g_{iso}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel} (G)
[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na 1	2.045	2.20	2.08	170
[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na 2	2.034	2.22	2.06	175
[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na 3	2.029	2.25	2.05	160
[(L ¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L ¹)]Na 4	2.038	2.29	2.04	173
[(L ²)Cu-Im-Cu(L ²)]Na 5	2.069	2.28	2.03	165

Cu(L)]Na **1** and [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2** of H_2L in polycrystalline state is shown in Fig. 1 and the EPR parameters calculated from their respective spectra are given in Table 2. The $\Delta M_s = \pm 1$ regions of EPR spectra of homonuclear complex [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1** showed two broad signals at -3080 and 3500 G.

The parallel and perpendicular components of separations d_{\parallel} and d_{\perp} are derived from the following expres-

sions : $d_{\parallel} = 2/D/g_{\parallel}$ and $d_{\perp} = D/g_{\perp}$. Where D is the zero-filled splitting parameter. The two broad signals at 3080 and 3500 G were thus assigned to the split g_{\perp} signal, allowing the calculation of zero-filled splitting parameter (D). Analysis of the spectrum gave the following values : $D = 0.04 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $g_{\parallel} = 2.20$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.08$. The value of D is consistent with those of other binuclear $Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}$ complexes²².

Room temperature polycrystalline EPR spectra of complex [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2** is of an axial pattern with $g_{\parallel} = 2.375$ and $g_{\perp} = 1.98$ and on the g_{\parallel} component is supported as a four-line hyperfine structure due to the copper nucleus. Axially symmetric complexes exhibits the features of $S = 1/2$, keeping in mind in this regards that we are observing the doublet ground state ($S_t = 1/2$) arising from the antiferromagnetic exchange coupling between $S_{Cu} = 1/2$ and $S_{Ni} = 1$ in the $Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}$ containing binuclear units. The four hyperfine line in spin coupled $Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}$ are easy to understand, as only Cu has isotope only ^{63}Cu (69.1%) and ^{65}Cu (30.9%) with $I_{Cu} = 3/2$, whereas Ni has isotope ^{61}Ni with $I_{Ni} = 3/2$, but its natural abundance is very low (1.25%). Thus the hyperfine structure due to only the copper nucleus is observed for exchanged-coupled $Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}$. Similar observations were comparable with reported binuclear imidazolite-bridged $Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}$ complexes²². The spectra of hetero-binuclear complexes [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na **3**, [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4** and [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(L²)]Na **5**, exhibit the usual line shape

for mononuclear copper(II) complexes with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.003$, indicating axial symmetry ($d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state).

Interestingly, the EPR spectra of **3-5** are similar. For each complex spectral feature of RT and LNT was also similar. The $g = 2$ signals for these complexes was broad and nearly isotropic. This is suggestive of the presence of spin-spin interactions which may be only intermolecular type in case of hetero-binuclear complexes **3**, **4** and **5**. Complexes **3-5** also showed weak half-field ($\Delta M_s = 2$) signal at RT and LNT. The signals ($\Delta M_s = 2$) for the hetero-binuclear bridged complexes **3-5** are quite strong and has been attributed to intermolecular spin-spin interactions arising due to solid effect^{23,24}.

Solution stability of $[Cu_2(Im)]^-$, $[Cu, Ni(Im)]^-$ and $[Cu, Zn(Im)]^-$ units :

The solution EPR spectra of $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ **1**; $[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ **2**; $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na$ **3**, in frozen 50% aq. DMSO solutions as a function of pH, have been recorded. The pH of the solution in the range 3.50 to 11.50 pH unit was adjusted using $HClO_4$ and $NaOH$ solutions. The pH dependent EPR spectral parameters are given in Table 3. Attempts were made to study the species formed due to breaking of imidazolate bridged. In complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ **1**, the EPR spectrum reflects the presence of at least four axially or nearly axially species in solution, possibilities for which are given as $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]^-$, $[(L)Cu-(ImH)]$; $[(L)Cu-OH_2]$ and $[Cu(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$. The presence of aqua species $[Cu(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$ was verified by observing g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} at 2.315 and 2.066, respectively, with $A_{\parallel} = 130$ G for a frozen solution of cupric perchlorate dissolve in the same solvent. At pH 4.50, the g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} parameters reveals the presence of species $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]^-$ and $[(L)Cu-(ImH)]$; the latter having $A_{\parallel} = 165$ G. As the pH increases, the A_{\parallel} values also increase to 170

G, suggesting the formation of imidazolate-bridged binuclear species $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ **1**. In the pH range 6.50–10.50, there is no specific change in the EPR parameters and in EPR features. This is suggestive that the imidazolate-bridged is intact in this pH range. Complex **1** dissociate according to :

In case complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ **2**, the similarity in spectra in the pH range 6.50–11.50 shows that the imidazolate-bridged is intact in this pH range. As pH is lowered to 4.50, the spectra show more frequent changes, at this pH, the presence of two species are characterized having g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} values corresponding to mononuclear species $[(L)Cu-OH_2]$ and $[Cu(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$. Evidently, as the pH is lowered, the imidazole bridged of the binuclear complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ **2** breaks on nickel side as per dissociation equilibrium :

Further, on lowering the pH up to 3.0, in the EPR features, in the EPR features again two distinct species was observed. One of the peak features corresponding to mononuclear complex $[(L)Cu-OH_2]$ and other features have characteristics attributable to $[Cu(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$.

In complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na$ **3**, in the pH range 4.50–11.50, this complex showed well-resolved EPR fea-

Table 3. pH dependent EPR parameters (in polycrystalline and 100% DMSO) for imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes **1-3**

pH/ Parameters	$[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ 1			$[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ 2			$[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na$ 3		
	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel}
10.50	2.223	2.025	170	2.215	2.048	175	2.210	2.058	170
8.50	2.230	2.021	170	2.213	2.042	176	2.206	2.055	174
7.15	2.228	2.032	172	2.215	2.042	175	2.220	2.059	175
6.50	2.210	2.045	170	2.214	2.044	175	2.208	2.052	173
4.50	2.305	2.047	165	2.238	2.041	170	2.218	2.059	175
3.00	2.315	2.066	130	2.315	2.066	125	2.370	2.070	120

tures for this single binuclear species. This is indicative that the binuclear species are intact in this pH range. On lowering the pH (i.e. 3.00), the presence of new peak features correspond to mononuclear complex [(L)Cu-(ImH)] and others features have characteristics attributed to species $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. This aqua species was verified by observing g -tensor at $g_{\parallel} = 2.370$, $g_{\perp} = 2.070$ and A_{\parallel} (G) = 120 G, which is quite close to those of $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ in the same frozen solution²⁵. Evidently, as the pH is lowered, the imidazole bridged of the binuclear complex [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2** breaks on zinc side as per dissociation equilibrium :

Superoxide dismutase activity determination :

These complexes exhibit significant catalytic activity towards the dismutation of superoxide anion. The superoxide was generated from alkaline DMSO and SOD activity was evaluated by the NBT assay. The count fraction causing 50% inhibition of NBT reduction is called IC_{50} concentration, equivalent to one unit of SOD activity (IC_{50} values), together with the IC_{50} values of native SOD are given in Table 4. The observed SODs (IC_{50} values) of imidazole-bridged binuclear complexes **1-5** ($\text{IC}_{50} = 27$

$\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **1**, $\text{IC}_{50} = 29 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **2**, $\text{IC}_{50} = 32 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **3**, $35 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **4** and $38 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ for **5**, respectively) was higher than the value exhibited by the native enzyme ($\text{IC}_{50} = 0.04 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) on a molar base (note that the smaller the IC_{50} value, the higher the SOD activity). The SOD activity of present complexes in the increasing order $5 > 4 > 3 > 2 > 1$, where it appears that the inclusion of ONO donor ligands ($\text{H}_2\text{L}/\text{H}_2\text{L}^1/\text{H}_2\text{L}^2$) reduce the SOD activity. The observed IC_{50} values of the present complexes are comparable with the various reported values for the imidazole-bridged binuclear complexes²⁶⁻²⁹, but are less active than the native SOD. A strong ligand field may oppose the interaction of copper with superoxide radicals, unfavouring the probable formation of intermediate copper superoxide adduct. In conclusion, the present imidazole-bridged complexes **1-5** of $\text{H}_2\text{L-H}_2\text{L}^2$ appears to be a fairly good models for the copper(II) site of intact Cu_2 , Zn_2 -SOD because these showed several structural and spectroscopic features similar to the active site of the enzyme.

Antibacterial activity against pathogens :

In the present investigation the antibacterial activity of synthesized binuclear complexes was studied. The antibacterial activity of imidazole-bridged binuclear complexes was evaluated against *E. coli*, *Streptococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi* pathogens. These activities were determined at three concentrations i.e. 10, 20, and 30 mM of each compound in DMSO and result were compared with lower concentration of standard antibiotic (chloramphenicol). Each experiment was performed in triplicate. Complexes [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1**; [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2**, [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na **3** and [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4** have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*. The susceptibility of certain strains of bacteria towards the present copper(II) complexes was determined by measuring the size of inhibition diameter. The bacteria are pathogens for humans, which causes dysentery food poisoning and typhoid, respectively. They inhibited the bacterial growth up to 18–29% at 30 mM whereas others have poor antibacterial activity^{30,31}. These complexes show lower activity than the known antibiotic chloramphenicol with **1** being more active than **2-4**.

The antibacterial activity of complexes [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1**; [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2**, [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na

Table 4. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity of some imidazole-bridged complexes

Sl. no.	Imidazole-bridged complexes	IC_{50} (mol dm^{-3})	Ref.
1.	[(dien)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	69.1	26
2.	[(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	43.0	26
3.	[bis(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	56.5	26
4.	[(terpy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(tren)] ³⁺	111.1	26
5.	[(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(bis(bipy))] ³⁺	49.7	26
6.	[bis(bipy)-Cu-Im-Zn-(bis(bipy))] ³⁺	58.5	26
7.	Native SOD	0.04	26
8.	[(tren)-Cu-E-Im-Zn-(tren)](ClO ₄) ₃	81	18
9.	[(tren)-Cu-E-Im-Ni-(tren)](ClO ₄) ₃	95	18
10.	[(salval)-Cu-Im-Cu-(salval)]Na	26	29
11.	[(salval)-Cu-Im-Ni-(salval)]Na	23	29
12.	[(salval)-Cu-Im-Zn-(salval)]Na	22	29
13.	[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na 1	27	This work
14.	[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na 2	29	This work
15.	[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na 3	32	This work
16.	[(L ¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L ¹)]Na 4	35	This work
17.	[(L ²)Cu-Im-Zn(L ²)]Na 5	38	This work

3 and $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(L^1)]Na$ 4 was graphically presented in Figs. 2 and 3 and results of these antibacterial assessments of binuclear complexes was shown in Table 5. The antibacterial (antimicrobial) data shows that in the three binuclear complexes *E. coli* is more susceptible in com-

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum of the complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ 1 of H_2L and $[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ 2 of H_2L in polycrystalline state at RT.

Fig. 2. Antibacterial activity of complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ 1 and $[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ 2 of H_2L .

parison to *Streptococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi* and antimicrobial activity of these compounds was increasing

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of complex $[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na$ 3 and $[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(L^1)]Na$ 4.

Table 5. Antibacterial activity of imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes 1-4

Complexes (mM)	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)		
	<i>Streptococcus aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
$[(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na$ 1			
10	7	9	6
20	15	17	14
30	21	24	19
$[(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na$ 2			
10	6	7	4
20	11	15	9
30	18	23	16
$[(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na$ 3			
10	6	8	5
20	13	15	11
30	18	20	17
$[(L^1)Cu-Im-Zn(L^1)]Na$ 4			
10	2	5	4
20	10	14	9
30	16	19	15

order. So that order of antibacterial activity of three compounds was as follows : [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1** > [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na **3** > [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2** > [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4**. It has been proved from data that complex [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1** was most effective which inhibit the growth of all tested bacteria and zone of inhibition was greater than *Streptococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*. Complex [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4** was least effective. Similar antibacterial results were reported by Tarafder *et al.*³².

Conclusion

The purpose of the synthesizing imidazolate-bridged binuclear complexes (Schemes 3 and 4) is to study as models for the active site of the bovine erythrocyte superoxide dismutase that would be helpful in understanding of some mechanistic fundamental aspects of the enzymes as well as to the development of structure activity relationship. The hetero-metallic complexes would provide interesting models to study the mechanism of O₂⁻ dismutation. Complexes [(L)Cu-Im-Cu(L)]Na **1**; [(L)Cu-Im-Ni(L)]Na **2**; [(L)Cu-Im-Zn(L)]Na **3**; [(L¹)Cu-Im-Zn(L¹)]Na **4**; [(L²)Cu-Im-Zn(L²)]Na **5**, were synthesized and characterized by different physico-chemical and spectroscopic techniques.

The copper(II) is a useful paramagnetic probe of protein structure and therefore is an important to ascertain the nature of its amino acid, peptide and protein complexes. The present synthesized imidazolate-bridged complexes **1-5** appears to be good models for the active site in [Cu₂, Cu₂-SOD], [Cu₂, Ni₂-SOD] and [Cu₂, Zn₂-SOD]. These complexes showed similar features in common with [Cu₂, Cu₂-SOD], [Cu₂, Ni₂-SOD] and [Cu₂, Zn₂-SOD] subunits. In particular, EPR, magnetic susceptibility measurement and SOD data are closed to proteins. As this article, herein we adds substantial data to the chemistry of [Cu₂, Zn₂-SOD] models and is therefore, relevant to the biochemistry of this element.

Strong antiferromagnetic coupling was usually observed in these binuclear metal proteins. Additionally, binuclear compounds can be interesting catalysts for reaction of hydrogen peroxide, occurring via two electron transfer. Complexes **1-4** have shown excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* comparable to that of *Streptococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*. The study of synthetic metal

complexes would be helpful in the search of some novel chemotherapeutic species to answer the emerging problem of the drug resistance in the health sciences.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from Technical Education Quality Improvement Programmed [NIT Patna Scheme No. TEQIP/58/2015-16) (S. Bharti), India is thankfully acknowledged.

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